

IDENTIFYING QUALITY CONTENTS OF N-LIST E-RESOURCES FOR ACADEMIC PURSUITS AND LEARNING OUTCOMES

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Abstract *This research paper explains the usage of the N-LIST E-resources among the student and faculty members of the various select Degree Colleges affiliated to Panjab University, Chandigarh. A questionnaire method was used as a tool for collection of data from the 32 select degree colleges in Punjab and Chandigarh. The total data was collected from the 466 out of 513 respondents. The total response rate is 90.84%. Out of 466 respondents, total 286 are users (faculty and student) respondents and 180 are non-users (faculty and student) non-users respondents. The statistical test has been applied and the inferences have been drawn thereof for identifying the quality of N-LIST E-resources for aiming users' academic pursuits and learning outcomes.*

Keywords: *E-Books, E-Journals, Bibliographical Databases, N-LIST, INFLIBNET, Academic Pursuits, Learning Outcomes, Degree Colleges of Panjab University*

INTRODUCTION

With the advent of resource sharing, the Library Consortia have brought economy, efficiency and equality in information availability and its usage. Through Library Consortia, the gap between information resource-rich libraries and resource-deficient libraries is expected to be bridged. Although, there are many consortia in India like UGC-INFONET Digital Library Consortia, INDEST Consortia, CSIR Consortia etc which have already gained the popularity in India. Yet, N-LIST is one of such consortia which helps to bridge this gap and provides access to the E-resources to its users.

N-LIST: AN INITIATIVE OF NMEICT

The National Mission on Education through Information and Communication Technology (NMEICT) was launched on 3rd Feb, 2009. It initiated a project called "National Library and Information Services Infrastructure for Scholarly Content (N-LIST)", popularly known as N-LIST which was formally launched by Shri Kapil Sibal, Union Minister for Human Resource Development, on 4th May, 2010. (ref. 1) The N-LIST Project is being jointly executed by the (University Grants Commission- Information

Network) UGC-INFONET Digital Library Consortium, INFLIBNET Centre and the INDEST-AICTE Consortium, Indian Institute of Technology (IIT) Delhi. The project provides the cross-subscription to e-resources subscribed by the two Consortia, i.e. subscription to INDEST-AICTE resources for universities and UGC-INFONET resources for technical institutions; and the access to selected e-resources to colleges.

The Faculty and the students from the colleges covered under section 12B/ 2F of UGC Act are eligible to access e-resources through the N-LIST project. These colleges are required to register themselves on the N-LIST Website. During the last three years, the collection has increased from 2,100 to 6,000 e-journals and from 51,000 to 1, 00,000 e-books (ref. 2 homepage), subscribed under the N-LIST Project.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Akinola (2009) obtained the results from her study which revealed that majority of the respondents (35.4%) from the University of Ibadan sought information to update knowledge. It was also found that the respondents also sought information for writing of papers or books, reading, and for

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preparing class lectures. The study on Information seeking behaviour of Social Science Faculty was done by Chattwal (2014) which indicates the pen-drive is most preferred as an external storage device due to its large storage capacity as well as convenience of usage was found to be the most preferred by 50.20% participants database appears to be the most suitable usage pattern for the University faculty members. Present study indicates that the main reasons for not using N-LIST E-resources are due to 'lack of awareness' by student non-users respondents. A similar study by Nikam & Pramodini (2007) indicates that reasons of non-use of UGC-INFONET resources by the Faculty Members and research scholars was 59.50% of respondents attributed the reason as lack of training/ orientation. The other reason included 28.50% of respondents attributed the reasons as 'lack of awareness' whereas 10.50% opted 'Aware but internet connection is not proper'. The authors concluded that the use was marginal and the scientist in the Mysore University Campus need constant guidance and training to maximise the use of UGC-INFONET e-resources. The similar study by Bhardwaj & Walia (2012) analyse the rating of the quality of the Electronic Resources in the St. Stephens College library, where majority of the respondents (52.8%) agreed that the 'Quality of the N-LIST e-resources are excellent' while 39.68% of the respondents rated the quality of the N-LIST e-resources were good. The authors also concluded that most of the respondents rated N-LIST e-resources very good. The similar study by Chikkanmanju and Kumbar (2015) identified the level of satisfaction of student respondents about the information retrieved through the N-LIST E-resources of the Tumkur University. The study reveals that 46.86% opined that the aided college students are extremely satisfied with the information retrieved through the N-LIST E-resources.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The present study is an attempt to find out the accessibility of N-LIST E-resources and the usage trends used by the faculty and students of the Panjab University, Chandigarh.

The study was conducted with the following objectives:-

1. To analyse the level of satisfaction amongst the faculty members for achieving their academic pursuits.
2. To analyse the level of satisfaction amongst the students for improving their learning outcomes.

HYPOTHESIS

Hypotheses H₀ 1 (A) - The faculty are dissatisfied with the N-LIST e-resources for achieving their academic pursuits.

H₁ 1(A) - The faculty are satisfied with the N-LIST e-resources for achieving their academic pursuits.

Hypotheses H₀ 1 (B) – The student are dissatisfied with the N-LIST e-resources for improving their learning outcomes.

Hypotheses H₁ 1 (B) - The student are satisfied with the N-LIST e-resources for improving their learning outcomes.

METHODOLOGY AND SCOPE OF THE STUDY

A Survey method has been implemented to meet the objectives of the study. The author has collected the data through questionnaire method from the select Degree Colleges which are affiliated to Panjab University. The data have been collected from the 144 faculty users and 142 student users. In 144 faculty users, 114 are males and 30 are females whereas 142 student users, 33 are males and 109 are females. The statistical ANOVA-test has been applied to approve the null or alternate hypothesis. This method facilitates yearly accumulation of information from the member colleges in various settings under parameters relevant to the study.

SCOPE AND LOCALE OF THE STUDY

This study is confined to 32 member colleges. These member colleges are located in Punjab and Chandigarh and are affiliated to Panjab University only.

TIME PERIOD OF THE STUDY

The time period of the study will be from Jan 2010 to May 2015.

DEMOGRAPHY

Demography refers to the fundamental and measurable statistics of a population with characteristics such as gender, age, education etc to which the faculty and student user belongs to. The table below will also provide demographic statistics of student Users' respondents in terms of gender, age, education. The analysis of the data has been done in the following manner:

Table 1: Demography Faculty & Student (User)

FACULTY (USER)		N (%)	STUDENT (Users)		N (%)
Gender N= 144	Male	30 (20.83%)	Gender N = 142	Male	33 (23.24%)
	Female	114 (79.17%)		Female	109 (76.76%)
Age N= 144	25-34	84 (58.33%)	Age N = 142	18-21	80 (56.34%)
	35-44	60 (41.67%)		22-24	58 (40.85%)
	Above 44	0 (0%)		Above 24	4 (2.82%)
Designation N= 144	Professor	3 (2.08%)	Education N = 142	Pursuing Graduate	23 (16.20%)
	Associate Professor	17 (11.81%)		Pursuing Post graduate	119 (83.80%)
	Assistant Professor	124 (86.11%)			

Gender

Fig. 1: Gender Wise Distribution of Respondents

The gender wise distribution of respondents is presented in the above figure. The responses have been received from

male and female respondents from the colleges through a detailed investigation. It has been analysed that out of 144 faculty users, 79.17% respondents are females while 20.83% are males whereas in the student users there are total 142 respondents from which 76.76% are the females and 23.24% are males. The above data reveals that the representation of female respondents is much more than that of the male respondents in both the categories.

TESTING OF HYPOTHESES

Hypotheses H₀ 1A - The Faculty are Dissatisfied with the N-LIST E-Resources for Pursuing Their Academic Pursuits.

Hypotheses H₁ 1A - The faculty are satisfied with the N-LIST E-resources for pursuing their academic pursuits.

Table 2: Faculty (Level of Satisfaction)

Sr. No.	Satisfaction/Relevance	Extremely satisfied	Moderately satisfied	Satisfied	Somewhat satisfied	Not satisfied	Total
		N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	
1.	Subject Coverage and its Relevance	6 (4.17%)	8 (5.56%)	58 (40.28%)	0 (0.00%)	72 (50.00%)	144 (100.00%)
2.	Relevant Teaching material	8 (5.56%)	9 (6.25%)	97 (67.36%)	30 (20.83%)	0 (0.0%)	144 (100.00%)
3.	Quality Contents	11 (7.64%)	7 (4.86%)	91 (63.19%)	18 (12.50%)	17 (11.81%)	144 (100.00%)
4.	Professional Competency	11 (7.64%)	17 (11.81%)	80 (55.56%)	15 (10.42%)	21 (14.58%)	144 (100.00%)
5.	Research Aptitude and Quality	12 (8.33%)	31 (21.53%)	53 (36.81%)	41 (28.47%)	7 (4.86%)	144 (100.00%)
6.	Update Information	7 (4.86%)	21 (14.58%)	87 (60.42%)	29 (20.14%)	0 (0.00%)	144 (100.00%)
Chi-Square		175	P-value		.000**		
d.f.		20					

In order to determine the satisfaction level of faculty respondents for quality contents of the N-LIST E-resources.

By amalgamating the scores of 'Extremely satisfied' (ES) and 'Moderately satisfied' (MS), it was revealed that 29.86% (ES = 8.33% + MS = 21.53%) of faculty respondents were

extremely satisfied with the relevance of N-LIST E-resources for research aptitude followed by 19.45% (ES = 7.64% + MS = 11.81%) of respondents were extremely satisfied with the relevance of N-LIST E-resources for professional competency and quality contents. Whereas 9.73% (ES =

4.17% + MS = 5.56%) of the faculty respondents were either extremely/ moderately satisfied with the subject coverage / disciplines and its relevance.

From the scores of 'Satisfied', it was analysed that 67.36% and 63.19% of faculty respondents considered N-LIST E-resources relevant for teaching material and of good quality in their respective subjects. Whereas 55.56% of faculty respondents considered N-LIST E-resources relevant for professional competency. It was also perceived that 40.28% of faculty respondents were satisfied with the N-LIST E-resources. While 36.81% of faculty respondents who were satisfied with the statement that information of research aptitude and quality is useful.

From the scores of the 'Not Satisfied' and 'Somewhat satisfied', it has been perceived that the faculty respondents i.e. 50% were not satisfied with information retrieved for subject coverage and its relevancy followed by 14.58% who feels that the N-LIST E-resources did not help in earning professional competency. While 28.47% of respondents are somewhat satisfied with research aptitude and quality contents.

Present study includes the satisfaction level of the Faculty and student respondents using the N-LIST E-resources about its relevancy and subject coverage. The similar study by Bhardwaj & Walia (2012) analyse the rating of the quality of the Electronic Resources in the St. Stephens College library,

where majority of the respondents (52.8%) agreed that the 'Quality of the N-LIST e-resources are excellent' while 39.68% of the respondents rated the quality of the N-LIST e-resources were good. The authors also concluded that most of the respondents rated N-LIST e-resources very good. It was observed that most of the respondents desired for the training to use the available e-resources through workshops and lectures methods, respectively.

It is inferred that majority of the faculty respondents i.e. 67.36% and 63.19% are satisfied with information retrieved for teaching material are relevant and satisfied with the quality content in their specific subjects/disciplines. On combining the scores of likert scale, the 50% of the faculty respondents are satisfied with the subject coverage and its relevance while seeking information. While the calculated Chi-square value and p-value are 175 and the p-value is .000 which is significant at 5% level, hence the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternate hypothesis is accepted i.e. the faculty are satisfied with the N-LIST E-resources for pursuing their academic pursuits.

Hence, the findings reject the Null Hypothesis H_0 3A.

Hypotheses H_0 3B- The students are dissatisfied with the N-LIST E-resources for improving their learning outcomes.

Hypotheses H_1 3B- The students are satisfied with the N-LIST E-resources for improving their learning outcomes.

Table 3: Student Faculty (Level of Satisfaction)

Sr. No.	Satisfaction/ Relevance	Extremely satisfied	Moderately satisfied	satisfied	Somewhat satisfied	Not satisfied	Total
		N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	
1.	Subject Coverage and its Relevance	19 (13.38%)	10 (7.04%)	64 (45.07%)	49 (34.51%)	0 (0.00%)	142 (100.00%)
2.	Relevant learning material	18 (12.68%)	14 (9.86%)	73 (51.41%)	37 (26.06%)	0 (0.00%)	142 (100.00%)
3.	Quality Contents	22 (15.49%)	8 (5.63%)	77 54.23%	20 (14.08%)	15 (10.56%)	142 (100.00%)
4.	Relevant in competitive examination	22 (15.49%)	10 (7.04%)	67 (47.18%)	12 (8.45%)	31 (21.83%)	142 (100.00%)
5.	Better Score	26 (18.31%)	13 (9.15%)	40 (28.17%)	43 (30.28%)	20 (14.08%)	142 (100.00%)
6.	Update Information	20 (14.08%)	14 (9.86%)	50 (35.21%)	58 (40.85%)	0 (0.00%)	142 (100.00%)
Chi-Square d.f.		142 20	P-value		000**		

From combining the scores of 'Extremely satisfied' (ES) and 'Moderately satisfied' (MS), it was revealed that 27.46% (ES= 18.31%+ MS= 9.15%) of student respondents were extremely satisfied for achieving better score in examinations followed by 23.94% (ES= 14.08% + MS= 9.86%) of student respondents were extremely satisfied with the updated information. While 22.53% (ES=15.49%+MS=7.04%) of student respondents considered N-LIST E-resources relevant for competitive examinations also.

From the scores of Satisfied, it was gathered that 54.23% and 51.41% of student respondents considered the N-LIST E-resources are relevant for learning material and its quality content in subject disciplines, whereas 47.18% of student respondents are considered E-resources relevant for competitive examinations followed by 45.07% of students who were also satisfied for subject coverage and its relevancy.

From the scores of the 'Not Satisfied' and 'somewhat satisfied', it has been perceived that the student respondents

i.e. 20.83% were somewhat satisfied with information retrieved for competitive examinations whereas 14.08% of student respondents feels that the N-LIST E-resources didn't help in scoring better marks and 10.56% considered dissatisfaction regarding the quality contents of the N-LIST E-resources.

The similar study by Chikkanmanju and Kumbar (2015) identified the level of satisfaction of student respondents about the information retrieved through the N-LIST E-resources of the Tumkur University. The study reveals that 46.86% opined that the aided college students are extremely satisfied with the information retrieved through the N-LIST E-resources. But the present study inculcates the evaluations of faculty and students users categories.

While combining the scores of Useful, Moderately Useful and Extremely Useful, it was concluded that 65.49% of student respondents are satisfied with the N-LIST E-resources for their learning outcomes. As, the calculated Chi-square value and p-value are 142 and .000, which is significant at 5% level, hence we reject null hypothesis and accepts the alternate hypothesis i.e. the student are satisfied with the N-LIST E-resources for improving their learning outcomes.

Hence, the findings reject the Null Hypothesis H_0 3B.

FINDINGS

1. A majority of the faculty respondents i.e. 67.36% and 63.19% are satisfied with information retrieved for teaching material are relevant and satisfied with the quality content in their specific subjects/disciplines.
2. On combining the scores of likert scale, the 50% of the faculty respondents are satisfied with the subject coverage and its relevance while seeking information.
3. 50% were not satisfied with information retrieved for subject coverage and its relevancy followed by 14.58% who feels that the N-LIST E-resources did not help in earning professional competency.
4. A majority of student respondents i.e. 65.49% are satisfied with subject coverage and its relevancy of N-LIST E-resources.
5. It has been perceived that the 20.83% of student respondents were somewhat satisfied with information retrieved for competitive examinations whereas 14.08% of student respondents feel that the N-LIST E-resources did not help in scoring better marks.
6. It has been discerned that the faculty are satisfied with the N-LIST e-resources for fulfilling their academic pursuits and the students users are extremely satisfied with the N-LIST E-resources, as their learning outcomes has been improved a lot.

SUGGESTIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study at hand was focused on the evaluation of usage of N-LIST E-resources in the Select Degree Colleges Affiliated to Panjab University, Chandigarh. The libraries should endeavour to launch a marketing plan to promote the usage of N-LIST E-resources and its awareness among the users through email alerts, text messages, social networking sites, whatsapp groups, blogs, and wikis etc. It is suggested that the subscription cost of N-LIST E-resources should be reduced to the same as earlier for the Non-aided colleges also.

Further the research in this regard will widen the criteria of the study and identify as to how the faculty and the student from the member colleges affiliated to other Universities explore the usage of the N-LIST E-resources. The authors feel that there is a need for appropriate and constant evaluation of this study in order to enhance insight into the usage analysis and the relevance of the information retrieved from the N-LIST E-resources.

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